

Closed-Form Analytical Expressions for NACA 5-Digit Reflex Camber Line Design Parameters

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The breakpoint location r and scaling constant k_1 for NACA 5-digit reflex camber lines have historically required numerical integration. This paper presents closed-form expressions for all thin-aerofoil integrals governing the zero-moment and design-lift constraints. Using the substitution $x = \sin^2 \phi$, the singular integrals reduce to elementary functions involving $\arcsin(\sqrt{r})$, $\arccos(\sqrt{r})$, and polynomials in r and x_{mc} . The breakpoint parameter r is obtained by one-dimensional root-finding without numerical quadrature, and k_1 follows by direct evaluation of the lift-condition integrals. For representative reflex cases (221, 231, 241, 251), agreement with legacy tabulations is within a maximum $|r_{\text{comp}} - r_{\text{tab}}| = 9.85 \times 10^{-4}$ and a maximum relative error in k_1 of 1.67%, while independent quadrature verifies all design integrals to 10^{-16} – 10^{-19} agreement. The resulting quadrature-free framework enables efficient, reproducible, higher-precision camber-line design calculations.

Nomenclature

Roman Symbols

A_0, A_1, A_2	=	Fourier coefficients of camber line slope [-]
C_l	=	2D lift coefficient [-]
$C_{l,i}$	=	ideal/design lift coefficient (at α_i) [-]
$C_{m_{c/4}}$	=	pitching moment coefficient about quarter-chord [-]
$\frac{dy_c}{dx}$	=	camber line slope [-]
$I_1^{(l)}, I_2^{(l)}$	=	thin-aerofoil integrals for lift condition [-]
$I_1^{(m)}, I_2^{(m)}$	=	thin-aerofoil integrals for zero-moment condition [-]
k_1	=	primary camber line scaling constant [-]
k_2	=	secondary camber line scaling constant (reflex only) [-]
L	=	design lift coefficient digit in NACA designation [-]

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$\mathcal{P}(r, x_{mc})$	= polynomial in $I_1^{(m)}$ closed-form expression [-]
$\mathcal{Q}(r, x_{mc})$	= polynomial in $I_2^{(m)}$ closed-form expression [-]
$\mathcal{R}(r, x_{mc})$	= polynomial in $I_2^{(m)}$ closed-form expression [-]
$\mathcal{S}(r, x_{mc})$	= polynomial in $I_1^{(l)}$ closed-form expression [-]
$\mathcal{T}(r, x_{mc})$	= polynomial in $I_2^{(l)}$ closed-form expression [-]
TT	= maximum thickness percentage [%]
$\mathcal{U}(r, x_{mc})$	= polynomial in $I_2^{(l)}$ closed-form expression [-]
P	= camber position digit in NACA designation [-]
Q	= camber-line type digit in NACA designation [-]
r	= normalised chordwise location of camber line break [-]
x	= normalised chordwise coordinate, $0 \leq x \leq 1$ [-]
x_{mc}	= normalised chordwise location of maximum camber [-]
y_c	= camber line ordinate [-]

Greek Symbols

α	= angle of attack [rad]
α_i	= ideal angle of attack [rad]
ϕ	= substitution variable used for integral evaluation [rad]
$\phi_r = \arcsin(\sqrt{r})$	= substitution value at camber break [rad]
$\psi_r = \arccos(\sqrt{r})$	= complementary substitution value, $\psi_r = \frac{\pi}{2} - \phi_r$ [rad]
θ	= thin-aerofoil mapping coordinate [rad]

Subscripts/Superscripts

$c/4$	= quarter-chord
cf	= closed-form
comp	= computed (from evaluated integrals)
i	= ideal (design) condition
(l)	= lift condition integral
mc	= maximum camber
(m)	= moment condition integral
num	= numerical quadrature
pred	= predicted
tab	= tabulated

I. Introduction

THE NACA 5-digit aerofoil series, developed by the National Advisory Committee for Aeronautics (NACA) in the 1930s [1, 2], remains widely used in aircraft design due to its systematic parameterisation of camber and thickness distributions. The reflex camber line variant, denoted by the third digit being unity (e.g., NACA 23112), is specifically designed to achieve zero pitching moment about the quarter-chord (aerodynamic centre in thin-airfoil theory) - a desirable characteristic for flying wing and tailless aircraft configurations [4].

In the standard NACA five-digit notation NACA LPQTT, the first digit L encodes the ideal/design lift coefficient at ideal angle of attack, $C_{l,i} = 0.15L$; the second digit P prescribes the maximum-camber location $x_{mc} = P/20$ (as a fraction of chord); the third digit Q specifies the camber-line family, with $Q = 0$ for non-reflex and $Q = 1$ for reflex; and the final two digits TT give the maximum thickness ratio $t/c = TT/100$ [1–4].

The complete specification of a NACA 5-digit reflex camber line requires determination of two design parameters:

- 1) The breakpoint location r , which must satisfy the zero-pitching-moment constraint $C_{m_c/4} = 0$.
- 2) The scaling constant k_1 , which must satisfy the design lift coefficient constraint $C_{l,i} = 0.15L$.

Since the original NACA publications [1, 2], both parameters have been determined through iterative numerical methods, with tabulated values provided for standard configurations [3, 4]. While closed-form expressions for the aerodynamic coefficients of NACA 4-digit and 5-digit standard camber lines are well established in the literature [4, 5], the integrals arising in the design conditions for reflex camber lines are not, to the author’s knowledge, available in closed form in the open literature.

This paper presents closed-form analytical expressions for all thin-aerofoil design integrals governing both the zero-moment and design-lift conditions for NACA 5-digit reflex camber lines. The key contributions are:

- 1) Closed-form *definite* expressions for the moment integrals $I_1^{(m)}$ and $I_2^{(m)}$ arising from the zero-pitching-moment condition.
- 2) Closed-form *definite* expressions for the lift integrals $I_1^{(l)}$ and $I_2^{(l)}$ arising from the design lift coefficient condition.
- 3) A complete quadrature-free design workflow: the breakpoint parameter r is obtained by solving $I_1^{(m)} + I_2^{(m)} = 0$ using one-dimensional root-finding, followed by direct closed-form evaluation of k_1 from the lift integrals.
- 4) Explicit polynomial expressions for all coefficients appearing in the closed-form results, in terms of r and x_{mc} .
- 5) Numerical verification against NASA tabulated values and independent quadrature evaluation of the original integrals.

The remainder of this paper is organised as follows. Section II states the reflex camber-line formulation and the resulting thin-aerofoil design integrals for both constraints. Section III summarises the closed-form expressions for all integrals. Section IV presents the complete design procedure for determining r and k_1 . Section V validates the closed-form predictions against tabulated values [3] and independent quadrature. Detailed derivations are provided in Appendices A–C. MATLAB code and data supporting the validation will be provided as supplemental material.

II. Mathematical Formulation

A. Reflex Camber Line Geometry

The NACA 5-digit reflex camber line is defined piecewise as follows. For a given NACA $LPQTT$ designation, the input camber-location parameter used below is $x_{mc} = P/20$ (with $Q = 1$ for the reflex family considered here).

For the forward region $0 \leq x < r$:

$$y_c = \frac{k_1}{6} \left[(x-r)^3 - \frac{k_2}{k_1} (1-r)^3 x - r^3 x + r^3 \right] \quad (1)$$

For the aft region $r \leq x \leq 1$:

$$y_c = \frac{k_1}{6} \left[\frac{k_2}{k_1} (x-r)^3 - \frac{k_2}{k_1} (1-r)^3 x - r^3 x + r^3 \right] \quad (2)$$

The corresponding camber line slopes are:

For $0 \leq x < r$:

$$\frac{dy_c}{dx} = \frac{k_1}{6} \left[3(x-r)^2 - \frac{k_2}{k_1} (1-r)^3 - r^3 \right] \quad (3)$$

For $r \leq x \leq 1$:

$$\frac{dy_c}{dx} = \frac{k_1}{6} \left[3\frac{k_2}{k_1} (x-r)^2 - \frac{k_2}{k_1} (1-r)^3 - r^3 \right] \quad (4)$$

The ratio k_2/k_1 is determined by requiring maximum camber to occur at $x = x_{mc}$:

$$\frac{k_2}{k_1} = \frac{3(r-x_{mc})^2 - r^3}{(1-r)^3} \quad (5)$$

Substituting Eq. (5) into Eqs. (3)–(4) and simplifying yields the working forms of the camber line slopes.

For $0 \leq x < r$:

$$\left(\frac{dy_c}{dx} \right)_{<r} = \frac{k_1}{2} (x^2 - 2rx + 2x_{mc}r - x_{mc}^2) \quad (6)$$

For $r \leq x \leq 1$:

$$\left(\frac{dy_c}{dx} \right)_{\geq r} = \frac{k_1}{2(1-r)^3} (b_2 x^2 + b_1 x + b_0) \quad (7)$$

where the coefficients are:

$$b_2 = 3(r-x_{mc})^2 - r^3, \quad (8)$$

$$b_1 = 2r^4 - 6r^3 + 12r^2 x_{mc} - 6rx_{mc}^2, \quad (9)$$

$$b_0 = 3r^3 - r^2 - 2r^4 x_{mc} - 6r^2 x_{mc} + 2rx_{mc} + r^3 x_{mc}^2 + 3rx_{mc}^2 - x_{mc}^2. \quad (10)$$

B. Thin Aerofoil Theory

In classical thin-aerofoil theory [4, 5], the camber-line slope admits the Fourier cosine series under the transformation

$$x = \frac{1 - \cos \theta}{2}, \quad \theta \in [0, \pi] \quad (11)$$

The Fourier coefficients are:

$$A_0 = \alpha - \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^\pi \frac{dy_c}{dx} d\theta \quad (12)$$

$$A_n = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\pi \frac{dy_c}{dx} \cos(n\theta) d\theta, \quad n = 1, 2, 3, \dots \quad (13)$$

The lift and moment coefficients are given by:

$$C_l = 2\pi \left(A_0 + \frac{A_1}{2} \right) \quad (14)$$

$$C_{m_{c/4}} = \frac{\pi}{4} (A_2 - A_1) \quad (15)$$

C. Design Constraints

1. Constraint 1: Zero Pitching Moment

For a reflex camber line, the primary design requirement is zero pitching moment about the quarter-chord:

$$C_{m_{c/4}} = 0 \quad (16)$$

From Eq. (15), this requires $A_2 - A_1 = 0$, which leads to:

$$\int_0^\pi \frac{dy_c}{dx} (\cos 2\theta - \cos \theta) d\theta = 0 \quad (17)$$

This constraint is homogeneous in k_1 and determines r (and hence k_2/k_1) up to selection of the physically admissible root, but not the absolute camber magnitude.

2. Constraint 2: Design Lift Coefficient

The ideal angle of attack α_i is defined by $A_0(\alpha_i) = 0$, which eliminates the leading-edge singularity. The ideal (design) lift coefficient is then:

$$C_{l,i} = \pi A_1 = 2 \int_0^\pi \frac{dy_c}{dx} \cos \theta d\theta \quad (18)$$

For NACA 5-digit aerofoils, the design lift coefficient is prescribed as $C_{l,i} = 0.15L$, where L is the first digit of the

designation; this constraint uniquely determines the scaling constant k_1 .

D. Transformation to x -Domain

The trigonometric terms are converted using $\cos \theta = 1 - 2x$:

$$\cos \theta = 1 - 2x \quad (19)$$

$$\cos 2\theta = 2 \cos^2 \theta - 1 = 2(1 - 2x)^2 - 1 = 1 - 8x + 8x^2 \quad (20)$$

Therefore:

$$\cos 2\theta - \cos \theta = (1 - 8x + 8x^2) - (1 - 2x) = 8x^2 - 6x \quad (21)$$

For the differential, from $x = (1 - \cos \theta)/2$:

$$\frac{dx}{d\theta} = \frac{\sin \theta}{2} \quad (22)$$

Since $\sin^2 \theta = 1 - \cos^2 \theta = 1 - (1 - 2x)^2 = 4x - 4x^2 = 4x(1 - x)$:

$$\sin \theta = 2\sqrt{x(1 - x)} \quad (23)$$

Thus giving us the Jacobian:

$$d\theta = \frac{dx}{\sqrt{x(1 - x)}} \quad (24)$$

The limits transform as: $\theta = 0 \Rightarrow x = 0$ and $\theta = \pi \Rightarrow x = 1$.

E. Formulation of the Design Integrals

1. Moment Condition Integrals

Substituting into Eq. (17) and splitting at $x = r$:

$$\int_0^r \left(\frac{dy_c}{dx} \right)_{<r} \frac{(8x^2 - 6x)}{\sqrt{x(1 - x)}} dx + \int_r^1 \left(\frac{dy_c}{dx} \right)_{\geq r} \frac{(8x^2 - 6x)}{\sqrt{x(1 - x)}} dx = 0 \quad (25)$$

We define the moment condition integrals:

$$I_1^{(m)} \equiv \int_0^r \left(\frac{dy_c}{dx} \right)_{<r} \frac{(8x^2 - 6x)}{\sqrt{x(1 - x)}} dx \quad (26)$$

$$I_2^{(m)} \equiv \int_r^1 \left(\frac{dy_c}{dx} \right)_{\geq r} \frac{(8x^2 - 6x)}{\sqrt{x(1 - x)}} dx \quad (27)$$

The zero pitching moment condition becomes:

$$\boxed{I_1^{(m)} + I_2^{(m)} = 0} \quad (28)$$

2. Lift Condition Integrals

Substituting the Jacobian (24) into Eq. (18):

$$C_{l,i} = 2 \int_0^1 \frac{dy_c}{dx} (1-2x) \frac{dx}{\sqrt{x(1-x)}} \quad (29)$$

Splitting at $x = r$ and substituting the simplified slope expressions (6)–(7):

$$C_{l,i} = k_1 \left[I_1^{(l)} + \frac{1}{(1-r)^3} I_2^{(l)} \right] \quad (30)$$

where the lift condition integrals are:

$$I_1^{(l)} \equiv \int_0^r (x^2 - 2rx + 2rx_{mc} - x_{mc}^2)(1-2x) \frac{dx}{\sqrt{x(1-x)}} \quad (31)$$

$$I_2^{(l)} \equiv \int_r^1 (b_2x^2 + b_1x + b_0)(1-2x) \frac{dx}{\sqrt{x(1-x)}} \quad (32)$$

The design lift condition becomes:

$$\boxed{k_1 = \frac{C_{l,i}}{I_1^{(l)} + \frac{1}{(1-r)^3} I_2^{(l)}}} \quad (33)$$

III. Closed-Form Results

For clarity, we present the closed-form *definite* expressions first; full derivations appear in Appendices A–C.

A. Moment Condition Integrals

1. Integral $I_1^{(m)}$ over $0 \leq x < r$

$$\boxed{I_1^{(m)} = k_1 \left[\frac{5-8r}{16} \arcsin(\sqrt{r}) + \sqrt{r(1-r)} \cdot \mathcal{P}(r, x_{mc}) \right]} \quad (34)$$

where the polynomial $\mathcal{P}(r, x_{mc})$ is:

$$\mathcal{P}(r, x_{mc}) = \frac{80r^3 + 8r^2 + 14r - 15}{48} + 2rx_{mc}^2 - 4r^2x_{mc}. \quad (35)$$

2. Integral $I_2^{(m)}$ over $r \leq x \leq 1$

$$I_2^{(m)} = \frac{k_1}{(1-r)^3} \left[Q(r, x_{mc}) \arccos(\sqrt{r}) - \sqrt{r(1-r)} \cdot \mathcal{R}(r, x_{mc}) \right] \quad (36)$$

where the polynomial $Q(r, x_{mc})$ is:

$$Q(r, x_{mc}) = \frac{8r^4 - 29r^3 + 15r^2 + 48r^2x_{mc} - 30rx_{mc} - 24rx_{mc}^2 + 15x_{mc}^2}{16}, \quad (37)$$

and the polynomial $\mathcal{R}(r, x_{mc})$ is:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{R}(r, x_{mc}) = \frac{1}{48} \left[-80r^6 + 232r^5 + 192r^5x_{mc} - 278r^4 - 480r^4x_{mc} - 96r^4x_{mc}^2 + 153r^3 \right. \\ \left. + 528r^3x_{mc} + 240r^3x_{mc}^2 - 45r^2 - 276r^2x_{mc} - 264r^2x_{mc}^2 + 90rx_{mc} + 138rx_{mc}^2 - 45x_{mc}^2 \right] \end{aligned} \quad (38)$$

B. Lift Condition Integrals

1. Integral $I_1^{(l)}$ over $0 \leq x < r$

$$I_1^{(l)} = \left(r - \frac{1}{2} \right) \arcsin(\sqrt{r}) + \sqrt{r(1-r)} \cdot \mathcal{S}(r, x_{mc}) \quad (39)$$

where:

$$\mathcal{S}(r, x_{mc}) = \frac{1}{6} \left(3 - 4r - 8r^2 + 24rx_{mc} - 12x_{mc}^2 \right). \quad (40)$$

2. Integral $I_2^{(l)}$ over $r \leq x \leq 1$

$$I_2^{(l)} = \mathcal{T}(r, x_{mc}) \arccos(\sqrt{r}) - \sqrt{r(1-r)} \cdot \mathcal{U}(r, x_{mc}) \quad (41)$$

where:

$$\mathcal{T}(r, x_{mc}) = \frac{1-2r}{2} \left(r^3 - 3r^2 + 6rx_{mc} - 3x_{mc}^2 \right), \quad (42)$$

and:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{U}(r, x_{mc}) = \frac{1}{6} \left(8r^5 - 24r^4x_{mc} - 20r^4 + 12r^3x_{mc}^2 + 48r^3x_{mc} + 21r^3 \right. \\ \left. - 24r^2x_{mc}^2 - 48r^2x_{mc} - 3r^2 + 24rx_{mc}^2 + 6rx_{mc} - 3x_{mc}^2 \right). \end{aligned} \quad (43)$$

IV. Design Procedure

A. Solution for Breakpoint Parameter r

The zero-pitching-moment condition requires $I_1^{(m)} + I_2^{(m)} = 0$. Since both integrals contain the factor k_1 , which cancels, this yields a transcendental equation in r and x_{mc} only:

$$\boxed{\frac{5-8r}{16} \arcsin(\sqrt{r}) + \sqrt{r(1-r)} \cdot \mathcal{P}(r, x_{mc}) + \frac{\mathcal{Q}(r, x_{mc}) \arccos(\sqrt{r}) - \sqrt{r(1-r)} \cdot \mathcal{R}(r, x_{mc})}{(1-r)^3} = 0} \quad (44)$$

This equation is solved numerically for r given x_{mc} , but crucially, no numerical integration is required - all terms are evaluated in closed form. When multiple roots exist in $(0, 1)$, the physically admissible breakpoint must satisfy $r > x_{mc}$; the smallest such root is selected.

B. Solution for Scaling Constant k_1

Once r is determined, the scaling constant k_1 follows directly from Eq. (33). Substituting the closed-form expressions (39)–(41):

$$\boxed{k_1 = \frac{C_{l,i}}{\left(r - \frac{1}{2}\right) \arcsin(\sqrt{r}) + \sqrt{r(1-r)} \mathcal{S}(r, x_{mc}) + \frac{1}{(1-r)^3} \left(\mathcal{T}(r, x_{mc}) \arccos(\sqrt{r}) - \sqrt{r(1-r)} \mathcal{U}(r, x_{mc}) \right)} \quad (45)$$

For NACA 5-digit notation, $C_{l,i} = 0.15L$.

C. Complete Design Algorithm

Given a NACA $LPQTT$ designation with $Q = 1$ (reflex):

- 1) **Input:** Extract L and P from the designation. Compute $x_{mc} = P/20$ and $C_{l,i} = 0.15L$.
- 2) **Solve for r :** Find the root of Eq. (44) in the interval $(x_{mc}, 1)$ using a one-dimensional root-finding algorithm (e.g., bisection, secant, Newton–Raphson, Brent’s method, or regula falsi).
- 3) **Compute k_2/k_1 :** Evaluate Eq. (5).
- 4) **Compute k_1 :** Evaluate Eq. (45) with the known values of r , x_{mc} , and $C_{l,i}$.
- 5) **Compute k_2 :** $k_2 = (k_2/k_1) \times k_1$.
- 6) **Output:** Complete camber line parameters (r, k_1, k_2) .

All steps involve only closed-form evaluations and a single root-finding operation; no numerical quadrature is required.

V. Validation

The closed-form expressions derived in the preceding sections were validated against tabulated reference values for the NACA 5-digit reflex camber-line series as compiled by Ladson and Brooks [3]. We distinguish between: (i) *internal consistency* checks (e.g., design conditions evaluated with the closed forms), and (ii) *independent numerical* checks (direct quadrature of the original integral definitions).

A. Validation of Breakpoint Parameter r

The design parameter r was obtained by solving the design constraint

$$I_1^{(m)}(r; x_{mc}) + I_2^{(m)}(r; x_{mc}) = 0 \quad (46)$$

using MATLAB's `fzero`, with $I_1^{(m)}$ and $I_2^{(m)}$ evaluated analytically using the derived closed forms. Table 2 compares the resulting values with the tabulations [3].

Table 2 Comparison of computed r against tabulations [3] (differences computed using full-precision r_{comp} ; see Appendix D).

Designation	x_{mc}	r_{tab}	r_{comp}	$r_{\text{comp}} - r_{\text{tab}}$	$ (I_1^{(m)} + I_2^{(m)})_{\text{cf}} $
221	0.10	0.1300	0.1307	$+7.50 \times 10^{-4}$	4.84×10^{-17}
231	0.15	0.2170	0.2160	-9.85×10^{-4}	1.37×10^{-15}
241	0.20	0.3180	0.3179	-8.10×10^{-5}	6.74×10^{-16}
251	0.25	0.4410	0.4408	-1.70×10^{-4}	1.41×10^{-16}

The maximum absolute discrepancy is 9.85×10^{-4} , with a mean of 4.97×10^{-4} . The residuals $|(I_1^{(m)} + I_2^{(m)})_{\text{cf}}|$ at the computed solutions are 10^{-15} – 10^{-17} , indicating near machine-precision satisfaction of the design constraint. For reproducibility, the computed values to eight decimal places are provided in Appendix D.

B. Independent Quadrature Verification of Moment Integrals

To independently verify the closed-form expressions for $I_1^{(m)}$ and $I_2^{(m)}$, we evaluate the *original integral definitions* by numerical quadrature at the same (x_{mc}, r) pairs and compare against the corresponding closed-form values. The original x -space integrands contain integrable endpoint singularities through the Jacobian factor $1/\sqrt{x(1-x)}$. We apply the substitution $x = \sin^2 \phi$, under which

$$\frac{dx}{\sqrt{x(1-x)}} = 2 d\phi, \quad \phi \in [0, \pi/2], \quad \phi_r = \arcsin(\sqrt{r}),$$

so that $I_1^{(m)}$ and $I_2^{(m)}$ are evaluated by quadrature on $\phi \in [0, \phi_r]$ and $\phi \in [\phi_r, \pi/2]$, respectively, with smooth ϕ -space integrands. Table 3 confirms agreement between closed-form and quadrature evaluations at the level of 10^{-16} – 10^{-19} ,

providing stringent end-to-end verification of the moment integral derivations.

Table 3 Independent quadrature verification of moment integrals.

Case	x_{mc}	r	$ I_1^{(m,cf)} - I_1^{(m,num)} $	$ I_2^{(m,cf)} - I_2^{(m,num)} $	$ (I_1^{(m)} + I_2^{(m)})_{num} $
221	0.10	0.13074976	3.85×10^{-17}	9.22×10^{-19}	8.95×10^{-18}
231	0.15	0.21601450	1.08×10^{-17}	1.97×10^{-17}	1.38×10^{-15}
241	0.20	0.31791890	1.65×10^{-17}	5.77×10^{-17}	5.99×10^{-16}
251	0.25	0.44083034	8.67×10^{-18}	1.74×10^{-16}	4.16×10^{-17}

C. Independent Quadrature Verification of Lift Integrals

The same verification procedure was applied to the lift integrals $I_1^{(l)}$ and $I_2^{(l)}$. Table 4 confirms agreement between closed-form and quadrature evaluations at the level of 10^{-17} – 10^{-19} , providing complete verification of the lift integral derivations.

Table 4 Independent quadrature verification of lift integrals.

Case	x_{mc}	r	$ I_1^{(l,cf)} - I_1^{(l,num)} $	$ I_2^{(l,cf)} - I_2^{(l,num)} $
221	0.10	0.13074976	2.26×10^{-17}	3.39×10^{-19}
231	0.15	0.21601450	3.82×10^{-17}	6.45×10^{-18}
241	0.20	0.31791890	6.94×10^{-18}	1.33×10^{-17}
251	0.25	0.44083034	0	2.54×10^{-17}

D. Validation of Scaling Constant k_1

The scaling constant k_1 was computed using Eq. (45) with the analytically determined r values and compared against the tabulated values [3]. Table 5 presents the results.

Table 5 Comparison of computed k_1 values against tabulations [3].

Designation	x_{mc}	L	$(k_1)_{tab}$	$(k_1)_{comp}$	Absolute Error	Relative Error
221	0.10	2	51.990	51.120	0.870	1.67%
231	0.15	2	15.793	15.691	0.102	0.65%
241	0.20	2	6.520	6.507	0.013	0.19%
251	0.25	2	3.191	3.176	0.015	0.48%

Across these cases, k_1 is reproduced to within 1.7% of the tabulations. The largest discrepancies occur for the 221 and 231 cases, where k_1 is large owing to the small effective camber when $r \approx x_{mc}$. However, as demonstrated in Section V.F, these discrepancies *cannot* be attributed to the propagation of errors in r : a first-order sensitivity analysis predicts that the $O(10^{-3})$ differences in r would produce changes in k_1 of only $O(10^{-2})$, whereas the observed discrepancies are $O(10^{-1})$ to $O(1)$.

The discrepancies therefore reflect differences in the original tabulation methodology rather than errors in the present derivation. Possible sources include: (i) different numerical quadrature schemes or limited floating-point precision in the legacy NACA-era computations, (ii) rounding of intermediate parameters before computing k_1 , or (iii) minor differences in conventions or governing equations. Crucially, the closed-form lift integrals underlying Eq. (45) are independently verified against numerical quadrature to machine precision (Section V.C), confirming the analytical correctness of the present expressions. The closed-form k_1 values may therefore represent a more accurate evaluation than the legacy tabulations.

E. Verification of k_2/k_1 Ratio

As a supplementary check, the ratio k_2/k_1 was computed using Eq. (5) with the analytically determined r values and compared against the tabulated values [3]. Table 6 presents the results. The relative errors for the 221 and 231 cases appear large (up to 20%) but reflect the small magnitude of k_2/k_1 itself rather than a deficiency in the analytical expressions. As confirmed by the sensitivity analysis in Section V.F, these discrepancies are *fully explained* by the propagation of $\mathcal{O}(10^{-3})$ differences in r : the predicted discrepancies $\Delta(k_2/k_1)_{\text{pred}} = \frac{\partial(k_2/k_1)}{\partial r} \cdot \Delta r$ match the observed values to within $\approx 10\%$ (Table 7).

Table 6 Verification of k_2/k_1 ratio against tabulations [3].

Designation	$(k_2/k_1)_{\text{tab}}$	$(k_2/k_1)_{\text{comp}}$	Absolute Error	Relative Error
221	0.000764	0.000916	1.52×10^{-4}	19.85%
231	0.006770	0.006213	5.57×10^{-4}	8.22%
241	0.030300	0.030195	1.05×10^{-4}	0.35%
251	0.135500	0.134878	6.22×10^{-4}	0.46%

From Eq. (5), the ratio depends on the numerator $3(r - x_{mc})^2 - r^3$, which approaches zero as $r \rightarrow x_{mc}$. For the 221 case, $(r - x_{mc}) \approx 0.03$, so the numerator is $\mathcal{O}(10^{-3})$; a discrepancy of $\mathcal{O}(10^{-4})$ in r propagates to a comparable absolute error in k_2/k_1 , but represents a large fraction of the small ratio. Physically, small k_2/k_1 corresponds to minimal reflex in the aft region - the camber line is nearly cubic throughout - and in this limit the ratio becomes ill-conditioned with respect to r . For the 241 and 251 cases, the breakpoint lies further aft, $(r - x_{mc})$ is larger, and k_2/k_1 is correspondingly of order 10^{-2} to 10^{-1} . Here the same absolute errors in r produce relative errors below 0.5%, confirming that the closed-form expression is accurate and the apparent discrepancies for forward-camber cases are a quantitatively predictable consequence of parametric sensitivity rather than analytical error.

F. Sensitivity Analysis

The discrepancies observed in Sections V.D and V.E can be examined through a sensitivity analysis of how small perturbations in r propagate into k_2/k_1 and k_1 .

1. Sensitivity of k_2/k_1

From Eq. (5), the derivative of k_2/k_1 with respect to r is obtained via the quotient rule:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\frac{k_2}{k_1} \right) = \frac{[6(r - x_{mc}) - 3r^2] (1 - r)^3 + 3(1 - r)^2 [3(r - x_{mc})^2 - r^3]}{(1 - r)^6} \quad (47)$$

Table 7 presents the computed sensitivities and demonstrates that the observed discrepancies are well-predicted by the first-order approximation $\Delta(k_2/k_1)_{\text{pred}} \approx \frac{\partial(k_2/k_1)}{\partial r} \cdot \Delta r$.

Table 7 Sensitivity analysis for k_2/k_1 : comparison of predicted and actual discrepancies.

Designation	r	$\frac{\partial(k_2/k_1)}{\partial r}$	Δr	$\Delta(k_2/k_1)_{\text{pred}}$	$\Delta(k_2/k_1)_{\text{actual}}$
221	0.1307	0.206	$+7.50 \times 10^{-4}$	$+1.54 \times 10^{-4}$	$+1.52 \times 10^{-4}$
231	0.2160	0.555	-9.85×10^{-4}	-5.47×10^{-4}	-5.57×10^{-4}
241	0.3179	1.407	-8.10×10^{-5}	-1.14×10^{-4}	-1.05×10^{-4}
251	0.4408	3.938	-1.70×10^{-4}	-6.68×10^{-4}	-6.22×10^{-4}

The close agreement between predicted and actual discrepancies confirms that the k_2/k_1 differences arise entirely from the propagation of small errors in r . For the 221 case, $\partial(k_2/k_1)/\partial r \approx 0.21$; although this sensitivity is modest, the ratio $k_2/k_1 \approx 0.0009$ is itself small, so even minor absolute changes appear as large relative errors. The sensitivity increases as the breakpoint moves aft, reaching $\partial(k_2/k_1)/\partial r \approx 3.9$ for the 251 case, but the larger baseline value of $k_2/k_1 \approx 0.135$ renders these variations less significant in relative terms.

2. Sensitivity of k_1

The sensitivity of k_1 to perturbations in r is computed numerically from Eq. (45). Table 8 presents the results.

Table 8 Sensitivity analysis for k_1 : comparison of predicted and actual discrepancies.

Designation	r	$\frac{\partial k_1}{\partial r}$	Δr	$\Delta k_{1,\text{pred}}$	$\Delta k_{1,\text{actual}}$
221	0.1307	-13.5	$+7.50 \times 10^{-4}$	-0.010	-0.870
231	0.2160	+1.70	-9.85×10^{-4}	-0.002	-0.102
241	0.3179	+2.52	-8.10×10^{-5}	-0.000	-0.013
251	0.4408	+2.15	-1.70×10^{-4}	-0.000	-0.015

Unlike k_2/k_1 , the predicted discrepancies in k_1 from error propagation in r do *not* explain the observed differences. For example, in the 221 case, the sensitivity $\partial k_1/\partial r \approx -13.5$ with $\Delta r \approx 7.5 \times 10^{-4}$ predicts $\Delta k_1 \approx -0.01$, yet the actual discrepancy is -0.87 - nearly two orders of magnitude larger. This indicates that the k_1 discrepancies arise primarily from differences in how the original tabulations were computed, rather than propagation of r errors alone. Possible sources include: (i) different numerical quadrature schemes or precision in legacy computations, (ii) intermediate value rounding before computing k_1 , or (iii) slight differences in the governing equations/conventions used historically.

G. Graphical Validation

Figure 1 provides a visual summary of the agreement between the analytical $r(x_{mc})$ relation and the tabulated values [3]. The left panel shows the analytical mapping r versus x_{mc} (solid line), together with the tabulated points and the computed roots; the computed markers are visually coincident with the tabulated values. The dashed line $r = x_{mc}$ indicates the physically admissible region $r > x_{mc}$. The upper-right panel plots the signed discrepancy scaled by 10^4 , confirming deviations of order 10^{-3} . The lower-right panel shows $I_1^{(m)} + I_2^{(m)}$ as a function of r for each x_{mc} , demonstrating clear zero-crossings at the solution values.

Fig. 1 Graphical validation of the analytical r solution: (left) r versus x_{mc} comparing the analytical relation (solid line), tabulated values [3], and computed roots; the dashed line indicates $r = x_{mc}$; (upper right) signed discrepancy $r_{\text{comp}} - r_{\text{tab}}$ scaled by 10^4 ; (lower right) zero-crossing of $I_1^{(m)} + I_2^{(m)}$ versus r for each x_{mc} .

Figure 2 presents corresponding results for the scaling constant k_1 . The left panel shows the analytical $k_1(x_{mc})$ relation, which exhibits the expected asymptotic increase as x_{mc} decreases (requiring larger k_1 to achieve the design lift when the effective camber is reduced). The upper-right panel displays the signed discrepancy $(k_1)_{\text{comp}} - (k_1)_{\text{tab}}$, showing the largest deviation for the 221 case. The lower-right panel verifies that the design lift coefficient $C_{l,i} = 0.3$

(corresponding to $L = 2$) is correctly recovered across all cases, confirming internal consistency of the closed-form lift-integral formulation.

Fig. 2 Graphical validation of the analytical k_1 solution: (left) k_1 versus x_{mc} comparing the analytical relation (solid line), tabulated values [3], and computed values; (upper right) signed discrepancy $(k_1)_{\text{comp}} - (k_1)_{\text{tab}}$; (lower right) verification that the design lift coefficient $C_{l,i} = 0.3$ is recovered for all cases.

H. Discussion

The validation results demonstrate that the closed-form analytical framework reproduces the tabulated design parameters [3] to within $O(10^{-3})$ for r and $O(10^{-2})$ for k_1 across the representative cases 221, 231, 241, and 251. The sensitivity analysis (Section V.F) clarifies the origin and significance of the observed discrepancies.

- 1) **Breakpoint parameter r :** The computed values satisfy the zero-moment condition $I_1^{(m)}(r) + I_2^{(m)}(r) = 0$ to machine precision (10^{-15} – 10^{-17}), and agree with the legacy tabulations to within the expected rounding uncertainty associated with four-decimal-place reporting. In this sense, the closed-form moment framework should be interpreted as providing *higher-precision* breakpoint locations consistent with the original condition,

rather than merely reproducing rounded tabulated values.

- 2) **Ratio k_2/k_1 :** The discrepancies between computed and tabulated values are quantitatively explained by the propagation of $O(10^{-3})$ differences in r through the sensitivity $\partial(k_2/k_1)/\partial r$. This behaviour is consistent with the first-order estimate

$$\Delta\left(\frac{k_2}{k_1}\right) \approx \frac{\partial(k_2/k_1)}{\partial r} \Delta r, \quad (48)$$

and confirms that the closed-form expression for k_2/k_1 is verified. Practically, this implies that the legacy scatter in k_2/k_1 is an expected consequence of rounding in r , rather than an inconsistency in the present formulation.

- 3) **Scaling constant k_1 :** In contrast, the observed discrepancies in k_1 are not explained by r error propagation: the predicted perturbations based on $\partial k_1/\partial r$ are $O(10^{-2})$, while the tabulated differences are $O(10^{-1})$ to $O(1)$ for the cases considered. Given that the lift-condition integrals are independently verified by numerical quadrature to machine precision (Table 4), the most plausible explanation is that the tabulated k_1 values reflect differences in legacy computational methodology (e.g., historical quadrature, intermediate rounding, or implementation conventions), rather than deficiencies in the present closed-form derivation.
- 4) **Sensitivity near forward-camber reflex configurations:** The sensitivity results further show that when $r \approx x_{mc}$ (a regime characteristic of forward-camber reflex configurations), both k_2/k_1 and k_1 become more sensitive to the breakpoint location. In this regime, small perturbations in r can induce disproportionately large changes in the derived constants, underscoring the value of computing r to higher precision from the exact zero-moment condition rather than relying on four-decimal-place tabulations.

Finally, the analytical expressions are independently corroborated by direct numerical quadrature of the original integral definitions, yielding agreement at the level of 10^{-16} – 10^{-19} for the moment integrals (Table 3) and 10^{-17} – 10^{-19} for the lift integrals (Table 4). This provides stringent verification of the closed-form results and supports the use of the present framework as a higher-precision alternative to legacy tabulations.

I. Validation Metrics Summary

Table 9 summarizes the principal validation metrics.

Table 9 Summary of validation metrics (cases: 221, 231, 241, 251).

Metric	Value
Maximum $ r_{\text{comp}} - r_{\text{tab}} $	9.85×10^{-4}
Mean $ r_{\text{comp}} - r_{\text{tab}} $	4.97×10^{-4}
Maximum moment-condition residual $ I_1^{(m)}(r_{\text{comp}}) + I_2^{(m)}(r_{\text{comp}}) $	1.37×10^{-15}
Maximum $ (k_1)_{\text{comp}} - (k_1)_{\text{tab}} $	0.870
Maximum relative error in k_1	1.67%
Maximum $ (k_2/k_1)_{\text{comp}} - (k_2/k_1)_{\text{tab}} $	6.22×10^{-4}

J. Implications

The combined numerical, quadrature, and sensitivity results imply that:

- 1) The present framework provides *higher-precision* breakpoint locations r consistent with the exact zero-moment condition, beyond the four-decimal-place legacy tabulations.
- 2) The observed differences in k_2/k_1 are a predictable consequence of tabulated rounding in r , and therefore constitute an indirect verification of the closed-form k_2/k_1 expression.
- 3) In regimes where $r \approx x_{mc}$, the elevated sensitivity of both k_2/k_1 and k_1 makes higher-precision r values particularly valuable for robust parameter determination.

VI. Conclusion

Closed-form analytical expressions have been derived for all thin-aerofoil integrals arising in the design of NACA 5-digit reflex camber lines. The principal outcomes are:

- 1) The moment integrals $I_1^{(m)}$ and $I_2^{(m)}$ admit closed-form representations involving $\arcsin(\sqrt{r})$, $\arccos(\sqrt{r})$, and polynomial contributions \mathcal{P} , \mathcal{Q} , \mathcal{R} in r and x_{mc} .
- 2) The lift integrals $I_1^{(l)}$ and $I_2^{(l)}$ admit closed-form representations involving the same trigonometric functions and polynomial contributions \mathcal{S} , \mathcal{T} , \mathcal{U} .
- 3) The breakpoint parameter r is obtained by solving the transcendental condition $I_1^{(m)} + I_2^{(m)} = 0$ using one-dimensional root-finding, requiring no numerical integration.
- 4) The scaling constant k_1 is obtained by direct closed-form evaluation from the lift integrals and the design lift coefficient $C_{l,i} = 0.15L$.
- 5) The complete design workflow is quadrature-free: all integral evaluations are performed in closed form.

The resulting formulation replaces repeated numerical quadrature with analytically evaluable expressions, improving reproducibility and computational efficiency. Comparison against tabulated values [3] shows agreement at the $\mathcal{O}(10^{-3})$ level for r . For k_2/k_1 , a sensitivity analysis confirms that discrepancies are fully explained by the propagation of small errors in r . For k_1 , discrepancies of up to 1.7% are observed but cannot be attributed to r error propagation; independent quadrature verification of both moment and lift integrals to machine precision suggests the closed-form values may be more accurate than the legacy tabulations.

These results provide an analytically transparent and computationally efficient foundation for implementing and extending NACA 5-digit reflex camber-line design calculations beyond legacy tabulations.

A. Derivation of $I_1^{(m)}$: Region $0 \leq x < r$

The integral over the forward region takes the form:

$$I_1^{(m)} = \int_0^r \left(\frac{dy_c}{dx} \right)_{<r} \frac{(8x^2 - 6x)}{\sqrt{x(1-x)}} dx \quad (49)$$

For $0 \leq x < r$, the camber line slope using the $\frac{k_2}{k_1}$ substitution yields:

$$\left(\frac{dy_c}{dx} \right)_{<r} = \frac{k_1}{6} [3(x-r)^2 - 3(r-x_{mc})^2] = \frac{k_1}{2} [x^2 - 2xr + 2x_{mc}r - x_{mc}^2] \quad (50)$$

Substituting and expanding the product with $(8x^2 - 6x)$:

$$\left(\frac{dy_c}{dx} \right)_{<r} (8x^2 - 6x) = \frac{k_1}{2} [8x^4 - 16x^3r + 16x^2x_{mc}r - 8x^2x_{mc}^2 - 6x^3 + 12x^2r - 12xx_{mc}r + 6xx_{mc}^2] \quad (51)$$

Collecting terms by powers of x :

$$\left(\frac{dy_c}{dx} \right)_{<r} (8x^2 - 6x) = \frac{k_1}{2} [8x^4 + (-16r - 6)x^3 + (16x_{mc}r - 8x_{mc}^2 + 12r)x^2 + (6x_{mc}^2 - 12x_{mc}r)x] \quad (52)$$

The resulting forward integral becomes:

$$I_1^{(m)} = \frac{k_1}{2} \int_0^r [8x^4 + (-16r - 6)x^3 + (16x_{mc}r - 8x_{mc}^2 + 12r)x^2 + (6x_{mc}^2 - 12x_{mc}r)x] \cdot \frac{dx}{\sqrt{x(1-x)}} \quad (53)$$

A. Trigonometric Substitution

To evaluate the singular integral, we employ the substitution:

$$x = \sin^2 \phi, \quad dx = 2 \sin \phi \cos \phi d\phi, \quad \sqrt{x} = \sin \phi, \quad \sqrt{1-x} = \cos \phi, \quad \sqrt{x(1-x)} = \sin \phi \cos \phi \quad (54)$$

This transforms the measure:

$$\frac{dx}{\sqrt{x(1-x)}} = \frac{2 \sin \phi \cos \phi d\phi}{\sin \phi \cos \phi} = 2 d\phi \quad (55)$$

And subsequently transforms the integration interval:

$$x = 0 \Rightarrow \phi = 0, \quad x = r \Rightarrow \phi = \arcsin(\sqrt{r}) \quad (56)$$

The integral then becomes:

$$I_1^{(m)} = k_1 \int_0^{\arcsin(\sqrt{r})} [a_4 \sin^8 \phi + a_3 \sin^6 \phi + a_2 \sin^4 \phi + a_1 \sin^2 \phi] d\phi \quad (57)$$

where $a_4 = 8$, $a_3 = (-16r - 6)$, $a_2 = (16x_{mc}r - 8x_{mc}^2 + 12r)$ and $a_1 = (6x_{mc}^2 - 12x_{mc}r)$.

B. Reduction Formulas

The standard reduction formula for sine to the power of n is:

$$\int \sin^n \phi d\phi = -\frac{\sin^{n-1} \phi \cos \phi}{n} + \frac{n-1}{n} \int \sin^{n-2} \phi d\phi \quad (58)$$

Applying this recursively yields:

$$\int \sin^2 \phi d\phi = \frac{\phi}{2} - \frac{\sin \phi \cos \phi}{2} \quad (59)$$

$$\int \sin^4 \phi d\phi = \frac{3\phi}{8} - \frac{3 \sin \phi \cos \phi}{8} - \frac{\sin^3 \phi \cos \phi}{4} \quad (60)$$

$$\int \sin^6 \phi d\phi = \frac{5\phi}{16} - \frac{5 \sin \phi \cos \phi}{16} - \frac{5 \sin^3 \phi \cos \phi}{24} - \frac{\sin^5 \phi \cos \phi}{6} \quad (61)$$

$$\int \sin^8 \phi d\phi = \frac{35\phi}{128} - \frac{35 \sin \phi \cos \phi}{128} - \frac{35 \sin^3 \phi \cos \phi}{192} - \frac{7 \sin^5 \phi \cos \phi}{48} - \frac{\sin^7 \phi \cos \phi}{8} \quad (62)$$

C. Back-Substitution and Definite Evaluation

Back substituting the above integrals into $I_1^{(m)}$ and grouping variables, we arrive at the pre-evaluation definite integral of the form:

$$\begin{aligned} I_1^{(m)} = k_1 & \left[\left(\frac{35a_4}{128} + \frac{5a_3}{16} + \frac{3a_2}{8} + \frac{a_1}{2} \right) \phi + \left(-\frac{35a_4}{128} - \frac{5a_3}{16} - \frac{3a_2}{8} - \frac{a_1}{2} \right) \sin \phi \cos \phi \right. \\ & + \left(-\frac{35a_4}{192} - \frac{5a_3}{24} - \frac{a_2}{4} \right) \sin^3 \phi \cos \phi + \left(-\frac{7a_4}{48} - \frac{a_3}{6} \right) \sin^5 \phi \cos \phi \\ & \left. + \left(-\frac{a_4}{8} \right) \sin^7 \phi \cos \phi \right]_{\phi=0}^{\arcsin(\sqrt{r})} \end{aligned}$$

Let $\phi_r \equiv \arcsin(\sqrt{r})$, so that $\sin \phi_r = \sqrt{r}$ and $\cos \phi_r = \sqrt{1-r}$. The lower limit $\phi = 0$ contributes zero since $\phi|_{\phi=0} = 0$ and $\sin 0 = 0$. Hence

$$I_1^{(m)} = k_1 \left[A \phi_r + B \sin \phi_r \cos \phi_r + C_3 \sin^3 \phi_r \cos \phi_r + C_5 \sin^5 \phi_r \cos \phi_r + C_7 \sin^7 \phi_r \cos \phi_r \right],$$

where

$$A = \left(\frac{35a_4}{128} + \frac{5a_3}{16} + \frac{3a_2}{8} + \frac{a_1}{2} \right), \quad B = \left(-\frac{35a_4}{128} - \frac{5a_3}{16} - \frac{3a_2}{8} - \frac{a_1}{2} \right),$$

$$C_3 = \left(-\frac{35a_4}{192} - \frac{5a_3}{24} - \frac{a_2}{4} \right), \quad C_5 = \left(-\frac{7a_4}{48} - \frac{a_3}{6} \right), \quad C_7 = \left(-\frac{a_4}{8} \right).$$

Using

$$\sin \phi_r \cos \phi_r = \sqrt{r(1-r)}, \quad \sin^3 \phi_r \cos \phi_r = r\sqrt{r(1-r)}, \quad \sin^5 \phi_r \cos \phi_r = r^2\sqrt{r(1-r)}, \quad \sin^7 \phi_r \cos \phi_r = r^3\sqrt{r(1-r)},$$

we obtain the compact evaluated form

$$I_1^{(m)} = k_1 \left[A \arcsin(\sqrt{r}) + \sqrt{r(1-r)} \left(B + C_3r + C_5r^2 + C_7r^3 \right) \right].$$

After substituting a_4, a_3, a_2, a_1 and simplifying, we find

$$A = \frac{5-8r}{16}, \quad \left(B + C_3r + C_5r^2 + C_7r^3 \right) = \mathcal{P}(r, x_{mc}),$$

so that

$$I_1^{(m)} = k_1 \left[\frac{5-8r}{16} \arcsin(\sqrt{r}) + \sqrt{r(1-r)} \cdot \mathcal{P}(r, x_{mc}) \right] \quad (63)$$

where the polynomial $\mathcal{P}(r, x_{mc})$ is:

$$\mathcal{P}(r, x_{mc}) = \frac{80r^3 + 8r^2 + 14r - 15}{48} + 2rx_{mc}^2 - 4r^2x_{mc}. \quad (64)$$

B. Derivation of $I_2^{(m)}$: Region $r \leq x \leq 1$

The integral over the aft region takes the form:

$$I_2^{(m)} = \int_r^1 \left(\frac{dy_c}{dx} \right)_{\geq r} \frac{(8x^2 - 6x)}{\sqrt{x(1-x)}} dx. \quad (65)$$

For $r \leq x \leq 1$, the camber line slope for the reflex case is:

$$\left(\frac{dy_c}{dx} \right)_{\geq r} = \frac{k_1}{6} \left[3 \frac{k_2}{k_1} (x-r)^2 - \frac{k_2}{k_1} (1-r)^3 - r^3 \right], \quad (66)$$

where the ratio k_2/k_1 is determined by the maximum camber location:

$$\frac{k_2}{k_1} = \frac{3(r-x_{mc})^2 - r^3}{(1-r)^3}. \quad (67)$$

A. Expansion of the Integrand

Define the compact coefficient

$$b_2 \equiv \left(\frac{k_2}{k_1}\right) (1-r)^3 = 3(r-x_{mc})^2 - r^3, \quad (68)$$

so that $\frac{k_2}{k_1} = b_2/(1-r)^3$. Substituting into the slope gives

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{dy_c}{dx}\right)_{\geq r} &= \frac{k_1}{6} \left[3\frac{b_2}{(1-r)^3} (x-r)^2 - \frac{b_2}{(1-r)^3} (1-r)^3 - r^3 \right] \\ &= \frac{k_1}{6} \left[\frac{3b_2}{(1-r)^3} (x-r)^2 - b_2 - r^3 \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Expanding $(x-r)^2 = x^2 - 2rx + r^2$ and regrouping yields the quadratic form

$$\left(\frac{dy_c}{dx}\right)_{\geq r} = \frac{k_1}{2(1-r)^3} [b_2x^2 + b_1x + b_0] \quad (69)$$

with

$$b_2 = 3(r-x_{mc})^2 - r^3, \quad (70)$$

$$b_1 = 2r^4 - 6r^3 + 12r^2x_{mc} - 6rx_{mc}^2, \quad (71)$$

$$b_0 = 3r^3 - r^2 - 2r^4x_{mc} - 6r^2x_{mc} + 2rx_{mc} + r^3x_{mc}^2 + 3rx_{mc}^2 - x_{mc}^2. \quad (72)$$

Multiplying by $(8x^2 - 6x)$ yields

$$(b_2x^2 + b_1x + b_0)(8x^2 - 6x) = c_4x^4 + c_3x^3 + c_2x^2 + c_1x, \quad (73)$$

with coefficients

$$c_4 = 8b_2, \quad (74)$$

$$c_3 = -6b_2 + 8b_1, \quad (75)$$

$$c_2 = -6b_1 + 8b_0, \quad (76)$$

$$c_1 = -6b_0. \quad (77)$$

Therefore the aft-region integral becomes

$$I_2^{(m)} = \frac{k_1}{2(1-r)^3} \int_r^1 [c_4 x^4 + c_3 x^3 + c_2 x^2 + c_1 x] \frac{dx}{\sqrt{x(1-x)}}. \quad (78)$$

B. Trigonometric Substitution

To evaluate the singular integral, we employ the same substitution as in Appendix A:

$$x = \sin^2 \phi, \quad dx = 2 \sin \phi \cos \phi d\phi, \quad \sqrt{x(1-x)} = \sin \phi \cos \phi, \quad (79)$$

so that

$$\frac{dx}{\sqrt{x(1-x)}} = 2 d\phi. \quad (80)$$

The limits transform as

$$x = r \Rightarrow \phi = \phi_r \equiv \arcsin(\sqrt{r}), \quad x = 1 \Rightarrow \phi = \frac{\pi}{2}. \quad (81)$$

Hence

$$I_2^{(m)} = \frac{k_1}{(1-r)^3} \int_{\phi_r}^{\pi/2} [c_4 \sin^8 \phi + c_3 \sin^6 \phi + c_2 \sin^4 \phi + c_1 \sin^2 \phi] d\phi. \quad (82)$$

C. Reduction Formulas

Using the same antiderivatives as in Appendix A:

$$\int \sin^2 \phi d\phi = \frac{\phi}{2} - \frac{\sin \phi \cos \phi}{2}, \quad (83)$$

$$\int \sin^4 \phi d\phi = \frac{3\phi}{8} - \frac{3 \sin \phi \cos \phi}{8} - \frac{\sin^3 \phi \cos \phi}{4}, \quad (84)$$

$$\int \sin^6 \phi d\phi = \frac{5\phi}{16} - \frac{5 \sin \phi \cos \phi}{16} - \frac{5 \sin^3 \phi \cos \phi}{24} - \frac{\sin^5 \phi \cos \phi}{6}, \quad (85)$$

$$\int \sin^8 \phi d\phi = \frac{35\phi}{128} - \frac{35 \sin \phi \cos \phi}{128} - \frac{35 \sin^3 \phi \cos \phi}{192} - \frac{7 \sin^5 \phi \cos \phi}{48} - \frac{\sin^7 \phi \cos \phi}{8}. \quad (86)$$

D. Back-Substitution and Definite Evaluation

Back substituting into $I_2^{(m)}$ and grouping terms gives the pre-evaluation definite integral:

$$I_2^{(m)} = \frac{k_1}{(1-r)^3} \left[\left(\frac{35c_4}{128} + \frac{5c_3}{16} + \frac{3c_2}{8} + \frac{c_1}{2} \right) \phi + \left(-\frac{35c_4}{128} - \frac{5c_3}{16} - \frac{3c_2}{8} - \frac{c_1}{2} \right) \sin \phi \cos \phi \right. \\ \left. + \left(-\frac{35c_4}{192} - \frac{5c_3}{24} - \frac{c_2}{4} \right) \sin^3 \phi \cos \phi + \left(-\frac{7c_4}{48} - \frac{c_3}{6} \right) \sin^5 \phi \cos \phi \right. \\ \left. + \left(-\frac{c_4}{8} \right) \sin^7 \phi \cos \phi \right]_{\phi_r}^{\pi/2}.$$

Let $\phi_r = \arcsin(\sqrt{r})$, so $\sin \phi_r = \sqrt{r}$ and $\cos \phi_r = \sqrt{1-r}$. At the upper limit $\phi = \pi/2$,

$$\sin\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right) \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right) = 0,$$

and all $\sin^{2n+1} \phi \cos \phi$ terms vanish. Thus

$$I_2^{(m)} = \frac{k_1}{(1-r)^3} \left[\left(\frac{35c_4}{128} + \frac{5c_3}{16} + \frac{3c_2}{8} + \frac{c_1}{2} \right) \left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \phi_r \right) \right. \\ \left. - \sqrt{r(1-r)} \left(\left(-\frac{35c_4}{128} - \frac{5c_3}{16} - \frac{3c_2}{8} - \frac{c_1}{2} \right) + \left(-\frac{35c_4}{192} - \frac{5c_3}{24} - \frac{c_2}{4} \right) r \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. + \left(-\frac{7c_4}{48} - \frac{c_3}{6} \right) r^2 + \left(-\frac{c_4}{8} \right) r^3 \right) \right].$$

Using $\frac{\pi}{2} - \arcsin(\sqrt{r}) = \arccos(\sqrt{r})$ gives the compact evaluated form

$$I_2^{(m)} = \frac{k_1}{(1-r)^3} \left[Q(r, x_{mc}) \arccos(\sqrt{r}) - \sqrt{r(1-r)} \mathcal{R}(r, x_{mc}) \right],$$

where $Q(r, x_{mc})$ and $\mathcal{R}(r, x_{mc})$ are obtained by collecting coefficients in the above expression.

After simplifying, we obtain:

$$\boxed{I_2^{(m)} = \frac{k_1}{(1-r)^3} \left[Q(r, x_{mc}) \arccos(\sqrt{r}) - \sqrt{r(1-r)} \cdot \mathcal{R}(r, x_{mc}) \right]} \quad (87)$$

where the polynomial $Q(r, x_{mc})$ is:

$$Q(r, x_{mc}) = \frac{8r^4 - 29r^3 + 15r^2 + 48r^2 x_{mc} - 30r x_{mc} - 24r x_{mc}^2 + 15x_{mc}^2}{16}, \quad (88)$$

and the polynomial $\mathcal{R}(r, x_{mc})$ is:

$$\mathcal{R}(r, x_{mc}) = \frac{1}{48} \left[-80r^6 + 232r^5 + 192r^5 x_{mc} - 278r^4 - 480r^4 x_{mc} - 96r^4 x_{mc}^2 + 153r^3 \right. \\ \left. + 528r^3 x_{mc} + 240r^3 x_{mc}^2 - 45r^2 - 276r^2 x_{mc} - 264r^2 x_{mc}^2 + 90r x_{mc} + 138r x_{mc}^2 - 45x_{mc}^2 \right] \quad (89)$$

C. Derivation of Lift Integrals $I_1^{(l)}$ and $I_2^{(l)}$

This appendix derives the closed-form expressions for the lift condition integrals used to determine k_1 .

A. Formulation

From Section II, the ideal lift coefficient is:

$$C_{l,i} = k_1 \left[I_1^{(l)} + \frac{1}{(1-r)^3} I_2^{(l)} \right] \quad (90)$$

where, with $E := 2rx_{mc} - x_{mc}^2$:

$$I_1^{(l)} = \int_0^r (x^2 - 2rx + E)(1 - 2x) \frac{dx}{\sqrt{x(1-x)}}, \quad (91)$$

$$I_2^{(l)} = \int_r^1 (b_2 x^2 + b_1 x + b_0)(1 - 2x) \frac{dx}{\sqrt{x(1-x)}}. \quad (92)$$

B. Expansion of Integrands

For region 1, expand:

$$(x^2 - 2rx + E)(1 - 2x) = -2x^3 + (1 + 4r)x^2 + (-2r - 2E)x + E \quad (93)$$

For region 2, expand:

$$(b_2 x^2 + b_1 x + b_0)(1 - 2x) = -2b_2 x^3 + (b_2 - 2b_1)x^2 + (b_1 - 2b_0)x + b_0 \quad (94)$$

C. Trigonometric Substitution

Apply the substitution $x = \sin^2 \phi$, $dx/\sqrt{x(1-x)} = 2 d\phi$:

$$I_1^{(l)} = 2 \int_0^{\phi_r} [-2 \sin^6 \phi + (1 + 4r) \sin^4 \phi + (-2r - 2E) \sin^2 \phi + E] d\phi \quad (95)$$

$$I_2^{(l)} = 2 \int_{\phi_r}^{\pi/2} [-2b_2 \sin^6 \phi + (b_2 - 2b_1) \sin^4 \phi + (b_1 - 2b_0) \sin^2 \phi + b_0] d\phi \quad (96)$$

D. Antiderivatives

The required antiderivatives are:

$$\int 1 d\phi = \phi \quad (97)$$

$$\int \sin^2 \phi d\phi = \frac{\phi}{2} - \frac{\sin \phi \cos \phi}{2} \quad (98)$$

$$\int \sin^4 \phi d\phi = \frac{3\phi}{8} - \frac{3 \sin \phi \cos \phi}{8} - \frac{\sin^3 \phi \cos \phi}{4} \quad (99)$$

$$\int \sin^6 \phi d\phi = \frac{5\phi}{16} - \frac{5 \sin \phi \cos \phi}{16} - \frac{5 \sin^3 \phi \cos \phi}{24} - \frac{\sin^5 \phi \cos \phi}{6} \quad (100)$$

E. Evaluation of $I_1^{(l)}$

At $\phi = \phi_r$: $\sin \phi_r = \sqrt{r}$, $\cos \phi_r = \sqrt{1-r}$, $\sqrt{r(1-r)} = \sin \phi_r \cos \phi_r = \sqrt{r(1-r)}$.

Collecting terms and simplifying:

$$I_1^{(l)} = \left(r - \frac{1}{2}\right) \phi_r + \sqrt{r(1-r)} \cdot \mathcal{S}(r, x_{mc}) \quad (101)$$

where:

$$\mathcal{S}(r, x_{mc}) = \frac{1}{6} \left(3 - 4r - 8r^2 + 24rx_{mc} - 12x_{mc}^2\right) \quad (102)$$

F. Evaluation of $I_2^{(l)}$

At $\phi = \pi/2$, all $\sin^m \phi \cos \phi$ terms vanish. At $\phi = \phi_r$, we use the same substitutions as above.

Using $\psi_r = \frac{\pi}{2} - \phi_r = \arccos(\sqrt{r})$:

$$I_2^{(l)} = \mathcal{T}(r, x_{mc}) \psi_r - \sqrt{r(1-r)} \cdot \mathcal{U}(r, x_{mc}) \quad (103)$$

where:

$$\mathcal{T}(r, x_{mc}) = \frac{1-2r}{2} \left(r^3 - 3r^2 + 6rx_{mc} - 3x_{mc}^2\right) \quad (104)$$

and:

$$\mathcal{U}(r, x_{mc}) = \frac{1}{6} \left(8r^5 - 24r^4 x_{mc} - 20r^4 + 12r^3 x_{mc}^2 + 48r^3 x_{mc} + 21r^3 - 24r^2 x_{mc}^2 - 48r^2 x_{mc} - 3r^2 + 24r x_{mc}^2 + 6r x_{mc} - 3x_{mc}^2 \right) \quad (105)$$

G. Final Expression for k_1

Substituting into the calibration formula:

$$k_1 = \frac{C_{l,i}}{\left(r - \frac{1}{2} \right) \phi_r + \sqrt{r(1-r)} \mathcal{S}(r, x_{mc}) + \frac{1}{(1-r)^3} \left(\mathcal{T}(r, x_{mc}) \psi_r - \sqrt{r(1-r)} \mathcal{U}(r, x_{mc}) \right)} \quad (106)$$

For NACA 5-digit aerofoils, $C_{l,i} = 0.15L$.

D. Extended-Precision r Values

For reproducibility, Table 10 reports computed r values to eight decimal places for the cases considered in Section V.A.

Table 10 Extended precision comparison for r (computed values to 8 decimal places).

Designation	x_{mc}	r_{tab}	r_{comp}	$r_{\text{comp}} - r_{\text{tab}}$
221	0.10	0.1300	0.13074976	$+7.4976 \times 10^{-4}$
231	0.15	0.2170	0.21601450	-9.8550×10^{-4}
241	0.20	0.3180	0.31791890	-8.1100×10^{-5}
251	0.25	0.4410	0.44083034	-1.6966×10^{-4}

Acknowledgments

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